

Analyzing Quantum Secure Direct Communication with Forward Error Correction

M. Iqbal^{1*}, M. Svaluto Moreolo¹, Arturo Villegas¹, Laia Nadal¹, and Luis Velasco²

¹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA) Castelldefels, Spain
²Optical Communications Group (GCO), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain
 e-mail: imasab@cttc.es

Abstract: We implement a quantum equivalent to classical QPSK communication on IBMQ and NetSquid. Results show that forward error correction fails to provide error-free transmission using near-term devices. Error-free transmission is possible when qubit fidelity reaches 0.981. © 2024 The Authors

1. Introduction

Quantum computing and communication bring powerful advantages over classical communication such as secure communication brought by quantum mechanics. Current transmission relies on classical data and classical channels, which are not inherently secure. A widely adapted approach to make them secure is encrypting the data via Quantum Key Distribution [1], which provides the secure key exchange for data encryption used for classical communication. Given the inherent properties of quantum principles, an alternative is to send classical data encoded in quantum bits (qubit) –the basic unit of quantum information. This would make the classical data inherently secure, avoiding the need for key distribution and encryption. To do so, Quantum Secure Direct Communication (QSDC)[2], a well-known quantum communication protocol can be exploited. QSDC transmits two classical bits using one qubit. We can envision this technique as a quantum equivalent to classical Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) modulation and call it Quantum-QPSK (Q²PSK). QPSK is a modulation technique used in classical communication, notable for its capacity to convey two bits per symbol. Each QPSK symbol encompasses 00, 01, 10, or 11.

The current landscape of quantum technologies is not mature and prone to several sources of noise [3], where actual quantum devices are not fault tolerant. Such devices are only capable of working with noisy qubits, because when a qubit interacts with the environment it decoheres and introduces errors. This limit: *i*) the functionality of these devices until *fault-tolerant* quantum devices become available; and *ii*) the implementation of Q²PSK as noise in qubits would result in high bit error rate (BER) defined as the number of bit errors per unit time. In this paper, we present the design and implementation of a Q²PSK highlighting its similarity to classical QPSK. It provides the telecommunications sector with a possibility to make the data inherently secure using quantum principles. We evaluate the performance of Q²PSK utilizing near-term quantum devices. The main contribution is to apply classical forward error correction (FEC) technique on classical data before modulation according to Q²PSK, that to the best of our knowledge has not been previously explored. This shows the improvement required in the near-term quantum devices to have error-free transmission using Q²PSK that is of particular relevance for future secure communications.

2. Design and Implementation of Q²PSK

Fig. 1 shows the design of Q²PSK, where Alice (A) sends classical information to Bob (B) encoded as quantum signal using quantum channel. To perform Q²PSK five blocks are required *i*) Entanglement pair generator (EG), which can be placed at any intermediate point between Alice and Bob; *ii*) Quantum memory [4]; *iii*) Quantum Modulator (QM); *iv*) quantum communication channel; and *v*) Quantum demodulator (QDM).

Firstly, ahead of time, the EG (labeled as 1 in Fig. 1), creates an entanglement pair. The quantum state of the qubit in the pair is highly correlated (the pair shares a superposition where either both are false, or both are true) no matter how far apart they are. Alice gets one half of the pair (2a), and Bob receives the other half (2b), and they store them in a quantum memory. Alice performs the quantum modulation and encodes classical data

Fig. 1: Design of Q²PSK

into her half of the entangled pair (3). The modulation is done by applying quantum gates, which perform quantum operations that change the qubit's state to a desired one, similar to classical logic gates. As an equivalent to QPSK, Alice can encode four possible messages 00, 01, 10 and 11: *i*) to send 00, Alice does not perform any operation; *ii*) for 01 she applies Z-gate that rotates the qubit 180° around Z-axis; *iii*) for 10 she applies X-gate that rotates qubit 180° around X-axis; and *iv*) for 11 she applies X and Z both gates. Alice sends her qubit to Bob using the quantum channel

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(4). Now, Bob has both halves of the entangled pair, but Alice has operated on one of them. Bob performs quantum demodulation (5) using a conditional-not (CNOT) gate on his qubit conditioned on Alice's qubit. This will flip the value of his qubit in the parts of the superposition where Alice's value is true. Then, Bob rotates Alice's qubit by 180° around the diagonal (X+Z) axis and finally, he measures the two qubits and retrieves the message.

The communication provided by Q²PSK is inherently secure. If an eavesdropper, Eve, intercepts Alice's qubit enroute to Bob, the information she obtains is part of an entangled state and she is unable to obtain information encoded in Alice's qubit because she lacks access to Bob's part of entangled qubit making the protocol inherently secure.

3. Test Setup and Results

Fig. 2 shows the setup implemented to evaluate the performance of Q²PSK. A back-to-back system is considered with EG, QM, and QDM. These blocks are modelled using gate model implementation of quantum circuits provided by IBM [5]. An entanglement pair is generated by applying Hadamard gate (H) followed by a CNOT gate. 4000 symbols are generated and encoded with a convolutional FEC. Encoded data is fed into a QM at Alice's side, which modulates her half of the pair. The data are sent to a QDM at Bob's side, which performs bell measurements, similar to the inverse of making a bell pair. After that, the FEC decoder recovers the signal. For FEC encoding and decoding, the FEC code rate of 2/3 is used, whereas the Viterbi decoding algorithm is applied at the receiver [6]. FEC encoding and decoding are performed offline in MATLAB.

As IBM provides a cloud-based service to access real NISQ quantum computers, we use the *ibmq-manila* and *ibmq-lima* noisy models as backend to mimic real quantum hardware. Table 1 presents the obtained BER calculated without FEC (pre-FEC) and with FEC (post-FEC). We observe that the devices improve the performance of the system with FEC but are unable to provide error-free transmission. This indicates that implementing Q²PSK using near-term quantum devices is not feasible. However, to study the required improvement of quantum hardware to provide error free transmission

using Q²PSK, a controlled simulation environment can be created. We implemented such environment on NetSquid [4], where the amount of noise injected into the quantum communication system is controlled. For simulation, depolarizing, phase damping, and amplitude damping noise are considered, that are the most common models to introduce qubit decoherence [7]. A useful metric to quantify the performance of a quantum system is fidelity, that describes the quality of the quantum state. A fidelity value of 1 means that it is in the desired state, while a value below 0.5 means that the state is no longer usable. Varying the noise will have direct impact on the fidelity of qubit state. We evaluated the performance of Q²PSK using the fidelity of Alice's qubit received by Bob ($f_{B<A}$) just before applying measurement (labeled as X in Fig. 2). For simulation, the ideal quantum circuit is considered and overall decoherence is applied at point X to reduce $f_{B<A}$. Fig. 3 demonstrates the results of pre-FEC BER and post-FEC BER as a function of $f_{B<A}$. If $f_{B<A}$ is low, then BER is high. Specifically, if $f_{B<A} < 0.981$, FEC fails to provide error-free transmission, but for $f_{B<A} \geq 0.981$ (i.e., below BER threshold of 1.05×10^{-2}), error-free transmission is observed. Thus, current quantum networks should be improved to provide $f_{B<A}$ values of at least 0.981 to have error-free transmission. Despite the inherent security the protocol faces challenges. This includes entanglement generation rate that directly impacts the data rate of Q²PSK, entanglement quality, and quantum memory. As an extension of this work, it would be interesting to investigate the achievable data rates based on available devices on different qubit platforms.

References

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Fig. 2 Test Setup

Table 1 Q²PSK performance on IBMQ devices

Quantum Device	Pre-FEC BER	Post-FEC BER
ibmq_lima	2.51e-02	1.78e-03
ibmq_manila	3.38e-02	1.73e-02

Fig. 3 Performance of Q²PSK